

Seeing is Believing: Using Visual Impact and Human Movement Data to Guide Wetland Restoration

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Summary

Wetland loss in Aotearoa New Zealand has been estimated at over 90%. Restoring wetlands provides significant opportunities for improving our ecosystems. Restoration efforts typically prioritize ecological and hydrological factors. However, understanding the visual impact of such restoration has the potential to improve public awareness of these sites. This paper proposes a visual impact methodology to support land use decision makers to identify potential areas for high visual impact. We use a weighted viewshed analysis to calculate the visibility of our study site and through the integration of human movement data, we move beyond visibility or viewshed calculations to assign weightings to each of these viewsheds to calculate the potential visual impact. We validated our visual impact method with a community group and our results show that the method is readily understood and provides value in identifying priorities for wetland restoration.

KEYWORDS: visual impact, viewshed, wetlands, human movement, restoration

1. Introduction

Wetlands play vital roles in the landscape: they act as natural filters, trapping pollutants and sediments before they reach waterways; they absorb floodwaters, helping to mitigate the effects of heavy rainfall; and they support rich biodiversity (Ferreira et al. 2023, Zedler & Kercher 2005). With over 90% of Aotearoa New Zealand's original wetlands lost since human settlement (Clarkson et al. 2013), restoring wetlands offers significant opportunities to improve ecosystem health and resilience. Restoration efforts typically prioritize ecological and hydrological factors (e.g. Tomscha et al. 2023, Zedler & Kercher 2005), but this research explores a different lens: how visible a potential restoration site is to people in the surrounding landscape. Underlying our approach is the expectation that if a restored wetland location is more visible to the surrounding landscape, more people will be aware of its benefits.

The visibility of wetlands is likely to lead to greater public appreciation for their natural beauty and ecological importance fostering greater support for conservation initiatives. There is a strong link between viewing green space and cognitive impacts, such as stress reduction and cognitive function (e.g. Liu et al. 2022). Public participatory mapping methods can help identify high visibility areas; however, little evidence suggests that such methods have been effectively used in decision making (Brown & Fagerholm 2015). In this paper, we propose a method to calculate the visual impact across a landscape to complement more participatory methods. Landscape visibility calculates what areas can be seen from single or multiple viewpoints (Inglis et al. 2022). Calculating visibility, however, is currently limited without an understanding of who can see the landscape. This project proposes to integrate human movement data with visibility analysis to address this issue and explicitly account for visual impact. We also work with a local environmental group to validate the data produced.

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Our proposed scalable approach can guide decision-making for wetland restoration efforts, ensuring ecological gains are paired with improved public awareness. By identifying locations where restored wetlands are both ecologically viable and highly visible, this approach could help increase public engagement and support for conservation initiatives. Such a method should be of interest to planners, conservationists, and local councils seeking to maximize the social and ecological benefits of wetland restoration projects.

2. Study Area

Our study area (Figure 1) was the Ruamāhanga Basin in the Wairarapa region of the North Island of Aotearoa New Zealand is a catchment of 3,361km². Predominantly an agricultural area (sheep, dairy, beef, and viticulture), the basin is home to approximately 50,000 residents. Two Māori iwi (tribes) (Ngāti Kahungunu ki Wairarapa and Ngāti Rangitāne o Wairarapa) have territorial ties to the basin. Compared with pre-human wetlands, the Ruamāhanga basin has suffered a loss is over 98% (~856km²) of its wetlands compared with pre-human wetland extents (Tomscha et al. 2019).

Figure 1 Study area: Ruamāhanga Basin, Aotearoa New Zealand

3. Methods

Viewshed analysis calculates the visible areas from specified observer points on a landscape represented by a Digital Elevation Model (DEM). By combining different viewsheds the visibility of a landscape can be calculated. The catchment boundary for the Ruamāhanga catchment was sourced from a layer of sea-draining catchments produced by the Department of Conservation (2010). The catchment boundary was buffered by 2km to overcome edge effects (where the viewshed is limited to observer points only within the catchment). Viewsheds were calculated using ESRI's ArcGIS Pro 3.4.0 Spatial Analyst on a 5m DEM based on lidar captured for Greater Wellington Regional Council by Aerial Surveys between 2013 and 2014.

Observer points were derived from the road and track networks in OpenStreetMap. An observer point was calculated at 1km intervals using 'Generate Points Along Lines', resulting in 2,032 points. A viewshed was calculated from each observer point to 5km. The observer height was set to 1m to simulate the height of a child or a driver in a car. The viewsheds were then summed with equal weighting to produce a visibility grid of the Ruamāhanga basin.

Figure 2 Subset of study area visual impact centred on the Waipoua river with extents of pre-human wetlands. **A.** No weighting applied to observer locations. **B.** Observer locations weighted using human movement data.

5. Community Validation

To test the validity of this approach for the potential users of the data, we shared our findings with a local community restoration group. Ethics approval was granted by Te Herenga Waka Victoria University of Wellington (#2024/HE000339). The restoration group are volunteers who meet regularly to undertake restoration efforts and to discuss how best to restore a sub catchment within the basin. The group saw potential in including visual impact in restoration planning, particularly as such wetlands could build awareness and support. They also emphasized the importance of combining this method with accurate, context-specific data, e.g. land use and land ownership. Our validation of both the visual impact methodology and results with a community group shows that the method is readily understood, differentiated from equally weighted visibility, and provides value in identifying priorities for wetland restoration.

6. Discussion and Conclusions

Gaining public support for landscape restoration efforts has the potential to magnify any ecological benefits of wetland restoration. This paper presents a landscape visibility methodology for assessing potential visual impacts, with the aim of supporting public awareness. Calculating the visual impact of different possible restoration sites won't (and shouldn't) replace ecological assessments, but such calculations add a new dimension to restoration planning by recognizing the importance of public engagement in a manner that can be easily considered beside other spatial factors. By including human movement data as captured via mobile phones, our visual impact method has identified the areas most and least visible in the landscape. Our validation with a community group shows that this data is both of interest to and understandable by these groups for restoration planning. The ease of creation as well as interpretation bodes well for integration into regional land use decision making.

Accessing human movement data can be difficult and also has an ethical dimension (e.g. opaque terms of reference may mean meaningful consent has not been granted (Bu-Pasha et al. 2016)). In future work, we aim to extend this project to simulate the human movement weighting through analysis of other data sources.

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Biographies

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Euan Forsyth is the Principal Spatial & Growth Analyst at Dunedin City Council, where he uses spatial data science to produce urban development insights. His research interests lay broadly in urban analytics, especially in urban morphology, retail geographies, walkability, and how complex systems interact to create a city.